

LITERATUURLIJST

door Drs. Th. P. van Hoorn

SIMULATIE

Algemeen

- Ch. P. Bonini: Simulation of information and decision systems in the firm. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1963.
- H. Guetzkow ed.: Simulation in social science. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1962.
- A. C. Hogatt en F. E. Balderston: Symposium on simulation models: Methodology and applications to the behavioral sciences. Cincinnati, Ohio 1963.
- G. H. Orcutt: Simulation of economic systems. The American Economic Review, Nr. 50, Dec. 1960, pag. 893-907.
- Martin Shubik: Simulation of the industry and the firm. The American Economic Review, Nr. 50, Dec. 1960, pag. 908-919.
- G. P. E. Clarkson and H. A. Simon: Simulation of group behaviour. The American Economic Review, Nr. 50, Dec. 1960, pag. 919-932.

Industrial Dynamics

- J. W. Forrester: Industrial dynamics - a major breakthrough for decision makers. Harvard Business Review, nr. 36, Juli/Aug. 1958, pag. 37-66.
- J. W. Forrester: Industrial dynamics. Cambridge, Mass. - New York, 1961.
- D. W. Packer: Resource acquisition in corporate growth. M.I.T., Cambridge, Mass. - New York, 1964.
- E. B. Roberts: Industrial dynamics and the design of management control systems. In: Management controls: New directions in basic research. Ch. P. Bonini, R. K. Jaedecke en H. M. Wagner, editors, New York, 1964.
- E. B. Roberts: The dynamics of research and development. London - New York, 1964.

SIMULATIEMETHODEN IN HET ONDERWIJS

Beslissingsspelen

1. Voor eerste kennisneming:

- K. Bleicher: Unternehmungsspiele. Baden-Baden 1962.
- K. Bleicher: Entscheidungssimulation und Unternehmungsspiele. Zeitschrift für Betriebswirtschaft 1962 nr. 1, pag. 15 e.v.
- Jay R. Greene en R. L. Sisson: Dynamic management decision games. New York 1959, en de Nederlandse bewerking hiervan:
- A. H. Hulshof en J. Ykel: Beslissingsspelen. Alphen a. d. Rijn, 1962.
- Paul S. Greenlaw, L. W. Herron en R. H. Rawdon: Business simulation in industrial and university education. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1962.

Th. P. van Hoorn: *Beslissingsspelen*. T.E.D. 1964, nrs. 1 en 2, pag. 31/36 en 63/68.

Joel M. Kibbee, C. J. Craft en B. Nanus: *Management games*. New York, 1961.

W. Rohn: *Führungsentscheidungen im Unternehmensplanspiel*. Essen 1964.

2. *Bijzondere onderwerpen:*

American Management Association: *Simulation and gaming, a symposium*.

A.M.A. Management report Nr. 55, 1961.

Bernard M. Bass: *Business gaming for organizational research*. Management science, vol. 10 nr. 3, april 1964, pag. 545-556.

Bernard M. Bass: *Some experimental approaches to the study of organization and psychology*. Management international, vol. 1963 nr. 3/4 pag. 90-97.

Kalman J. Cohen and Eric Rhenman: *The role of management games in education and research*. Management science nr. 7, jan. 1961.

Kalman J. Cohen e.a.: *The Carnegie Tech management game*. The journal of business, nr. 33, okt. 1960, pag. 303-321.

William R. Dill en Neil Doppelt: *The acquisition of experience in a complex management game*. Management science vol. 10 no. 1, oktober 1963, pag. 30-46.

F. J. Drenkhard, B. Gamer, K. Hax, H. Langer en G. Schätzle: *Unternehmungsspiele und ihre Bedeutung für die betriebswirtschaftliche Ausbildung an Hochschulen*. Zeitschrift für handelswissenschaftliche Forschung, 15e jaargang nr. 4, april 1963.

M. E. Fessler, C. B. Saunders en J. D. Steele: *Proceedings of the national symposium on management games*. Center for Research in Business, University of Kansas, May 1959.

L. W. Herron: *Executive action simulation*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1960.

E. W. Martin Jr.: *Management decision simulation*. Homewood Ill., 1960

K. J. Nijkerk en Th. P. van Hoorn: *Groepsobservatie en enquêtering tijdens beslissingsspelen*. Mens en Onderneming, Jan. 1964, pag. 30 e.v.

A. Rapoport en C. Orwant: *Experimental games: a review*. Behavioral science, vol. 7 no. 1, 1962, pag. 1-37.

Hans B. Thorelli en Robert L. Graves: *International operations simulation*. London 1964.

Cases

M. J. Dooher en V. Marquis: *The development of executive talent*. American Management Association, New York, 1952.

G. Dahlke en K. Agthe: *Die Fallmethode*. R.K.W. Schriftenreihe Betriebsführung und Fortbildung BF 3, Frankfurt/Main, 1960.

D. W. Hargreaves: *Case studies and projects*. In: *Management training techniques*. British Institute of Management, 1962.

E. Kilgus: *Die case method: ihre Möglichkeiten und Grenzen*. Die Unternehmung 1958 nrs. 5 en 6, pag. 184 en 201.

- E. Kosiol: Die Behandlung praktischer Fälle im betriebswirtschaftlichen Hochschulunterricht (Case Method). Berlin 1957.
- E. Kosiol: Using practical cases in university curricula for business management. Management International 1961, nr. 2 pag. 104.
- M. P. Mc Nair en A. C. Hersum: The case method at the Harvard Business School. New York - London 1954.
- H. B. Schmidt: Die Fallmethode (case study method). Essen 1958.

Rollenspel

- H. A. Hutte: Vorming van volwassenen door creatief spel. Purmerend 1956.
- A. F. Klein: Role playing in leadership training and group problem solving. New York 1956.
- Norman R. F. Maier: Principles of human relations. New York 1953, speciaal hoofdstukken IV en V.
- Norman R. F. Maier, A. R. Solem en A. A. Maier: Supervisory and executive development: a manual for role playing. London 1961.

Incidentmethode

- J. van Ierland: Case- en incidentmethode. Personeelsleiding 1956, 9e jaargang, nrs. 9 en 10.
- Paul and Faith Pigors: Case method on the spot. Adult Leadership dec. 1954.
- Paul and Faith Pigors: The incident process, learning by doing. Adult Leadership jan. 1955.
- Paul and Faith Pigors: Case study in human relations: What is it and what can it do? New York 1955.
- E. H. de Waal: De incidentmethode, opgevat als leervorm tot training in de situatieve denkwijze. Volksopvoeding, 7e jaargang nr. 1 jan/febr. 1958.

In-basket

- H. E. Frank en J. S. Pringle: „In-tray” training exercises. Several military and industrial applications of the English version of in-basket simulation. Training Directors Journal. April 1962, pag. 27 e.v.
- P. S. Greenlaw: The in-basket as a training instrument. In: Wenzil K. Dolva Ed.: Marketing keys to profits in the 1960's, pag. 452 e.v. Chicago, American Management Association, 1960.
- J. J. M. Penders: Kadervorming in de industrie. Utrecht-Antwerpen 1962, pag. 191 e.v.
- Charles D. Smith: „What's in the box, Doc?”. An in-basket test for young executives. Training Directors Journal. Jan. 1961, pag. 27 e.v.

Onderhandelingsoefeningen

- Wendell R. French: A collective bargaining game. *Training Directors Journal*, Jan. 1961, pag. 10-13.
- Harold Guetzkow e.a.: *Simulation in international relations. Developments for research and teaching*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1963.
- S. Siegel en L. E. Fouraker: *Bargaining and groupdecision-making: Experiments in bilateral monopoly*. New York 1960.
- A. A. Zoll: *Operation suburbia*. Boeing Airplane Cy. Seattle Wash.

Communicatie-oefeningen

- P. Hesselink: *Interne communicatie: experiment, spel en werkelijkheid*. T.E.D. 1963 nr. 7, pag. 392-398.
- A. N. Oppenheim: *Communication*, in: *Social psychology through experiment*, ed. by George Humphrey and Micheal Argyle, Londen 1962.

Voorts zij verwezen naar de in bovenstaande titels genoemde literatuur, alsmede naar die, vermeld in de bijdragen in dit nummer.